

MDPhar Semi-structured interview with lecturers

Interview questions

Question	ALACT phase
Describe how the students engaged with the learning of academic skills in the sessions you taught (pre-2020, 2020, 2022).	2: Looking back on the action
What benefit for student learning did you expect to see from implementing the ALACT model? Did student performance meet these expectations? Why or why not?	3: awareness of essential aspects
Where there any challenges or negative aspects for students? If yes, what do you think caused that? What might you adjust in the future to compensate or address that?	3: awareness of essential aspects 4: creating alternative methods of action

Remark related to publication

Although questions for the semi-structured interview were designed in English, the interviews themselves were held in Dutch, as this was the primary language for both the interviewer and the interviewees. The Dutch translation of these questions was corroborated by a second author.